

HCl) experiment, ^1H nmr and mass spectral analysis and by direct comparison with an authentic sample³. This is the first report of the isolation of auranti- amide acetate from a plant of Sterculiaceae family.

The air-dried and powdered leaves (1 kg) of *P. heyneanum* were successively extracted with n-hexane, chloroform and methanol. The defatted residue (5 g) from the n-hexane extract on column chromatography yielded lupeol acetate (100 mg), m.p. 211–12°; lupanone (80 mg), m.p. 204–05°; taraxerone (100 mg); friedelin (120 mg), taraxerol (200 mg) and β -sitosterol (400 mg). The residue (4 g) from the chloroform extract yielded kaempferol (100 mg), m.p. 277–78°. Methanol extract yielded no crystalline compound.

The co-occurrence of different groups of triterpenes in this plant is of biogenetic significance.

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Chemical Examination of *Tephrosia hamiltonii*

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THE genus *Tephrosia* elaborates several types of flavonoid compounds¹. Chemical investigation of *Tephrosia hamiltonii* (Fam.: Leguminosae) does not seem to have been reported so far. We now report the result of chemical investigation on this plant.

The air-dried pods of *T. hamiltonii* were extracted successively with petroleum ether, chloroform and methanol. The combined chloroform and methanol extracts, after the usual work up, followed by

column chromatography led to the isolation of two colourless compounds, designated as compound-A and -B.

Compound-A (1; 0.0075%), m.p. 150°, $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_8\text{O}_4$, M^+ 192, did not give any colouration with alcoholic FeCl_3 , but was soluble in aqueous NaHCO_3 and aqueous NaOH , indicating the presence of a carboxyl group; formed the liquid mono- methyl ester (2), $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_4$, M^+ 206, with diazo- methane, supporting the presence of one carboxyl group in 1; ν_{max} 1670br (carboxyl), 1595, 1540, 1465 (aromatic ring), 1065 (benzofuran) and 1230 cm^{-1} (aromatic C–O stretch); λ_{max} (MeOH) (log ϵ) 222 (4.65), 245sh (4.08) and 280 nm (3.36), similar to those of disubstituted benzofurans². The ^1H nmr spectra (90 MHz, CDCl_3) of compound-A, revealed the presence of one methoxyl group at δ 4.35 (3H, s) and two AB doublets, one at δ 7.75 (d, J 2.5 Hz) and 7.10 (d, J 2.5 Hz) assignable to H–2 and H–3 of benzofuran nucleus, respectively. Further, the nmr spectra also showed two ortho- coupled doublets at δ 7.46 (1H, J 9 Hz) and 8.2 (1H, J 9 Hz). The foregoing analytical and spectral data indicate that compound-A is a benzofuran derivative containing methoxyl and carboxyl groups on adjacent positions in the benzenoid ring and premitted four alternative isomeric structures (1, 3, 4 and 5). As ^1H nmr spectrum of 1 showed a

- 1, R = OCH_3 , R' = COOH
 2, R = OCH_3 , R' = COOCH_3
 3, R = COOH , R' = OCH_3
 4, R = OCH_3 , R' = COOH
 5, R = COOH , R' = OCH_3

doublet (δ 8.2) far down-field, structures 3 and 5 are ruled out. Since 1 (methylkaranjic acid) is reported in the literature³ as a degradation product of pongamol, an attempt was made to compare compound-A with methylkaranjic acid. A direct comparison of compound-A with an authentic sample of methylkaranjic acid revealed that they are identical in all respects (m.p., m.m.p., superim-posable ir). This is the first report of compound 1, as a natural product, though such simple benzo- furans with different substitution patterns are known to occur in plants belonging to Asteraceae⁴.

Compound-B (0.0075%), m.p. 140–42°. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_4$, M^+ 194, did not give any colour test. Its ir, uv, nmr and mass spectral data was strikingly similar to those reported for terephthalic acid⁵, which was

confirmed by a direct comparison with an authentic sample.

The powdered leaves of *T. hamiltonii* were successively extracted with petroleum ether, chloroform and methanol. The combined petroleum ether and chloroform extracts on column chromatographic separation (silica gel) yielded two colourless compounds, designated as C and D. Compound-C, crystallised from methanol as colourless needles (0.02%), m.p. 138°, $[\alpha]_D - 35^\circ$ (CHCl₃), gave positive Liebermann-Burchardt test for sterol and was characterised as β -sitosterol⁶ by direct comparison with an authentic sample. Compound-D, crystallised from benzene as colourless rhombic crystals (0.09%), m.p. 130°, C₂₈H₄₄O₄, M⁺ 294, gave characteristic colour reactions of pongamol⁷. From the spectral data (uv, ir, ¹H nmr, mass) and also by a direct comparison, compound-D was identified as pongamol. The ¹³C nmr spectra (90 MHz, CDCl₃) of pongamol reveal δ 180 (C=O), 184 (β , γ =O), 158.75 (C-4'), 153.81 (C-2'), 147.69 (C-6'), 144.32 (C-5'), 135.77 (C-1'), 132.14 (C-1), 128.62 (C-3'), 127.10 (C-4), 126.51 (C-2 and -6), 122.23 (C-3 and -5), 119.63 (C-5''), 107 (C- α), 105.32 (C-4'') and 61.116 (OCH₃).

The methanol extract of *T. hamiltonii* leaves, after preliminary purification gave a glycosidic fraction, which on column chromatographic purification (Sephadex-LH-20; eluent, MeOH) yielded compound-E, which was crystallised from methanol as pale yellow amorphous solid (0.11%), m.p. 189–90°, C₂₇H₃₂O₁₀, M⁺ 610. It gave magenta colour with Mg/HCl and responded positively to Molisch test suggesting it to be a flavonoid glycoside. Acid hydrolysis (7% methanolic H₂SO₄) of the glycoside yielded quercetin (m.p. 313°) and two sugars which were characterised as D(+)-glucose and L(-)-rhamnose by co-paper chromatography with authentic samples. From the analytical and spectral data (ir, uv, ¹H nmr, mass and ¹³C nmr) the glycoside was identified as rutin⁸, which was confirmed by a direct comparison with an authentic sample.

The powdered roots of *T. hamiltonii* were extracted successively with petroleum ether and chloroform. Elaborate column chromatography (silica gel) of the chloroform extract yielded two colourless crystalline compounds, designated as F and G. Compound-F (0.02%) was identified as pongamol. Compound-G was crystallised from chloroform as colourless needles (0.014%), m.p. 179–80°, C₁₇H₁₂O₅, M⁺ 296, ν_{\max} (KBr) 1 650 (unsaturation), 1 610, 1 570, 1 515 (aromatic ring), 1 460 (C–O), 1 240 (Ph–O), 1 040 (furan moiety) and 940 cm⁻¹ (OCH₃O); λ_{\max} (MeOH) (log ϵ) 212 (4.48), 240sh (4.40), 338 (4.50) and 355 nm (4.57); it was characterised as flemichapparin-B⁹. The ¹H nmr and mass spectral fragmentation pattern of the compound was in good agreement with those reported for flemichapparin-B⁹. The ¹³C nmr spectra (90 MHz, CDCl₃) of flemichapparin-B reveal δ 55.36 (OCH₃), 65.42 (C-6), 94.0 (C-10), 97.17 (C-4), 101.36 (OCH₃O), 102.50 (C-1'), 106.31

(C-6'), 107.20 (C-7), 109.87 (C-2), 119.17 (C-7'), 120.87 (C-1), 144.75 (C-8 and -9), 145.64 (C-11'), 150.50 (C-10'), 154.94 (C-4') and 160.89 (C-3). There appears to be no report on the occurrence of flemichapparin-B in a *Tephrosia* species.

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A New Flavone from *Cheilanthes farinosa* Kaulf.

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IN continuation of our previous works on plant pigments^{1,2} a systematic chemical examination of *Cheilanthes farinosa*³ (*Polypodiaceae*), on which no phytochemical work seems to have been reported so far, has been undertaken. *C. farinosa* is a small tufted fern very common in the hilly regions.

The air-dried powdered whole plant (aerial parts and roots) of *C. farinosa* was successively extracted with petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°) and chloroform. The concentrated petroleum ether extract was chromatographed over silica gel. Elution with benzene–chloroform (1:1) mixture afforded a yellow solid, crystallised from chloroform–methanol (5:1) mixture, m.p. 145°, C₁₈H₁₂O₆ (M⁺ 328). It gave greenish blue colour with ferric chloride and gave